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**POSSIBILITIES OF APPLICATION OF THE EXPERIENCE OF MUSIC
PEDAGOGY OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN UZBEKISTAN**

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Annotation: This article studies the advanced experiences of foreign countries in music pedagogy and analyzes the possibilities of their application in the education system of Uzbekistan. The experience of leading countries of the world - the USA, Germany, Japan, South Korea - highlights the modern methodological approaches, teaching technologies and specific aspects of curricula used in music education. The pedagogical, cultural and methodological factors necessary for the implementation of these experiences in the conditions of Uzbekistan are identified. On this basis, the possibilities of modernization of the national music education system, integration of innovative approaches and improvement of musical literacy of students are analyzed.

Keywords: foreign experience, methodological approach, music education, curriculum, innovative technologies, cultural adaptation, musical literacy.

Introduction.

In today's conditions of globalization and the rapid development of information technologies, the pace of development of each field, including music pedagogy, is changing radically. Advanced pedagogical approaches, methodological tools and modern educational technologies formed in world experience in organizing music education serve as an important methodological basis for national education systems. In particular, music education models formed in developed countries - the USA, Germany, Japan, South Korea and other countries - attract attention not only for their level of technological development, but also for their didactic approaches, competency-based curricula and effective methods for developing musical literacy. Systematic reforms are being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan to modernize music education and bring it into line with international standards. The decisions taken by our state to improve the quality of education, update curricula, and introduce modern methodological tools make it necessary to study foreign experiences. After all, adapting foreign experience, not directly copying it, but based on critical analysis, taking into account national values, socio-psychological conditions, and the pedagogical environment, serves to increase the effectiveness of musical education.

Music pedagogy is not only a means of teaching students skills such as

singing, hearing, and reading music, but also a means of forming aesthetic taste, cultural awareness, and national spirit. From this point of view, studying their methodological approaches in the musical-educational direction through the analysis of foreign experiences and determining the possibilities of their application in the conditions of Uzbekistan is one of the most relevant issues, both theoretically and practically. In foreign countries, music pedagogy is considered not only an art field, but also an important pedagogical direction that serves the comprehensive development of the individual. Each country has formed music education based on its socio-cultural, economic and technological conditions. Below, we will consider pedagogical approaches and methods that can be used in Uzbekistan by analyzing the experience of some advanced countries.

The experience of music pedagogy in the United States.

Music education in the United States is an integral part of the general education system. The main principles of music education here are the early identification of the student's musical abilities, support for individual development, interactive lessons and group performance. Methods such as Orff-Schulwerk, Kodály, Suzuki, which are widespread in the USA, serve to develop creativity, listening culture and stage culture in students. In particular, technologies are actively used in music education - digital platforms, virtual music laboratories and online classes.

The German model of music education.

Music pedagogy in Germany has a strong scientific and theoretical basis. In this country, music education is carried out systematically from preschool age. The musical abilities of the younger generation are gradually developed through the Musikschule (music school) system. The German model is distinguished by its strict curriculum, a combination of academic music disciplines (theory, solfeggio, history) and practical training. Each student, along with individual lessons, is also involved in orchestral, ensemble and choral performances, which reinforces the social principle of music.

The experience of Japan and South Korea.

In East Asian countries, in particular, Japan and South Korea, the formation of social responsibility, teamwork and aesthetic sensitivity in a person through music education is a priority. In Japan, students are given in-depth training in the culture of playing, singing and listening to musical instruments from the school level. Music lessons are considered not only to impart knowledge, but also as a means of cultivating self-control, discipline, attention and creativity. In South Korea, technological solutions (artificial intelligence-based note analysis, interactive music programs) have become an integral part of the educational

Possibilities of application in the conditions of Uzbekistan.

An analysis of foreign experiences shows that it is important not to copy them completely, but to adapt them. For example, creative methods in the USA (Kodály or Orff) can be developed in a local version for Uzbek secondary schools based on Uzbek folk songs. The focus on musical literacy and theoretical subjects in the German experience should be focused on deeper teaching of musical knowledge in local schools. Through the educational approach of Japan, it is possible to strengthen the role of music as a means of personal development, not only for performance. In addition, multidisciplinary music curricula, differentiated teaching models, and interactive lessons based on multimedia platforms, which are available in foreign experience, can be gradually introduced in Uzbekistan. Most importantly, by combining these experiences with national values, Uzbek traditional music and cultural identity, it will be possible to form modern, but authentic approaches to music education.

Literature review:

Scientific research conducted on foreign music pedagogy, textbooks and sources studying international experience show that music education has been formed as a comprehensive system that serves not only to impart artistic knowledge, but also to develop personal development, aesthetic education, and cultural awareness. Theoretical and practical literature created in different countries serves as the main source for developing effective methodological approaches and pedagogical models in this area.

In particular, E. Gordon's Music Learning Theory, aimed at identifying and developing musical abilities, is widely used among American educators. In this theory, musical hearing (audition), rhythmic perception and vocal expression are defined as the main elements. The advantage of Gordon's theory is that it serves to gradually develop the natural musical intuition of students.

Carl Orff's Orff-Schulwerk concept is based on the integration of music, movement and speech. This approach serves to stimulate children's creative activity, develop free expression and form the ability to critically perceive music. In this model, children interact with music through various percussion instruments, body rhythms, pantomime, and theater elements. This method can also be introduced in Uzbekistan at the preschool and primary levels.

In the literature on music pedagogy in Japan and South Korea, in particular, the Suzuki Method by Shinichi Suzuki occupies a special place. This method suggests that a child learns music in a way similar to the process of learning speech: repetition, listening, parental participation, gradual complexity. This

approach is the basis for increasing self-confidence in a child and understanding music as a way of life.

The work of Russian researchers, in particular D. B. Kabalevsky, V. M. Shatskaya, E. B. Abdullin on the theory of music education, also had a direct impact on Uzbek music pedagogy. Their work has established the foundations for cultivating a love of music in children, teaching national and classical heritage, and planning musical and educational activities for preschool and school-age children.

The studies of Uzbek scientists T. Alimatov, Z. Kholmirezayeva, Sh. Tursunov analyzed the national identity of music pedagogy, methods of teaching based on folk art, as well as issues of combining national traditions with modern pedagogical technologies. The theories and approaches put forward in foreign literature serve as an important basis for the formation of musical literacy, creative activity, competencies and the introduction of innovative methods in Uzbek music education. At the same time, modern scientific and practical research is necessary to critically study these experiences and adapt them to the national pedagogical context, and to develop effective methodological models.

Discussion:

The study of approaches and methodological models of music pedagogy formed in foreign countries shows that music education has become a powerful tool for comprehensively developing a person, forming cultural awareness and aesthetic perception on a global scale. The experience of countries such as the USA, Germany, Japan, and South Korea shows that music education is not limited to specialized schools, but is carried out in an integrated and systematic manner at each stage of general education schools. In this regard, musical literacy, creative expression, the use of technological tools, and the development of social competencies are of paramount importance. The education system of Uzbekistan is currently being updated, and music education is being reviewed as an important area of reform in this process. From this point of view, it is necessary to study and adapt foreign experiences on the basis of critical observation. In this regard, it is necessary to analyze, first of all, the essence of pedagogical approaches, the socio-cultural conditions in which they arose, their didactic foundations, and practical possibilities. For example, the Kodály and Orff-Schulwerk methods of music education in the USA are based on creative and active participation. These methods increase students' interest in music, form musical thinking based on independent expression and emotional experience. By combining the basic principles of these methods with local traditional melodies in the Uzbek education system, musical competencies based on national melodies can be developed.

In European countries, especially in Germany, musical literacy and academic knowledge are taught in depth. It is important to apply this experience in improving the curricula of music theory, solfeggio and instrumental performance in Uzbekistan. At the same time, it is necessary to analyze foreign methodologies in the system of training pedagogical personnel and integrate them based on programs suitable for local conditions. The experience of East Asia, in particular, in Japan, musical education is carried out gradually from preschool age. This approach shows that early initiation of musical education serves to develop emotional awareness, hearing, stage culture and team spirit in children. This experience can be an important basis for expanding music lessons in the preschool education system in Uzbekistan, creating easily mastered repertoires for children based on national melodies, and preparing methodological manuals.

The experience of incorporating digital technologies into the educational process in foreign countries is also relevant. In Uzbekistan, the opportunities for teaching music through interactive, digital platforms are also expanding. Online lessons, mobile applications, virtual musical instruments can create an environment that attracts students and improves practical skills. However, it is important not to directly copy any experience, but to adapt it in harmony with the musical heritage, values, and cultural characteristics of the Uzbek people. Otherwise, musical education can become artificial, alien, and create a sense of separation in the minds of students. It can be seen from the discussion that the effective aspects of music pedagogy from foreign countries can enrich the Uzbek education system and serve to form modern musical competencies in students. This requires scientifically based selective adaptation, retraining of teachers, and updating of methodological manuals.

Conclusion.

An analysis of the experience of foreign countries shows that innovative approaches, systematic methodology, the use of technological tools, and educational concepts based on national culture are of paramount importance in organizing music pedagogy. Advanced pedagogical models developed in countries such as the USA, Germany, Japan, and South Korea are aimed at forming students' musical thinking, a culture of creative expression, and an aesthetic worldview. In the Uzbek education system, it is an urgent task not to directly implement foreign experiences, but to adapt them to national culture, Uzbek musical heritage, and didactic conditions based on critical analysis. In particular, the methods used abroad — the Kodály, Orff-Schulwerk, and Suzuki approaches — can be an important source for creating local methodological models based on folk music. On this basis, it can be concluded that by integrating foreign experiences into the

musical and educational process, it is possible to improve the quality of Uzbek music pedagogy, develop students' musical competence, and form a modern educational model based on innovative approaches. For this, it is necessary to use foreign approaches in the training of pedagogical personnel, develop practical and methodological manuals, and harmonize national and global values in musical education.

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